

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Precise realtime current consumption measurement in IoT

TestBed [version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

Background: The Internet of Things, similar to wireless sensor networks, has been integrated into daily life of almost everyone. These wearable, stationary, or mobile devices are in multiple locations, collecting data or monitoring and executing certain tasks. Some can monitor environmental values and interact with the environment, while others are used for data collection, entertainment, or even life-saving. To achieve the wireless part of the system, the majority of sensor nodes are designed to be battery-powered. While battery power has become increasingly ubiquitous, it tends to increase the global carbon footprint of electronic devices. This issue can be mitigated by employing some form of energy harvesting so that batteries can be refilled and the gadget lasts longer, but this does not alter the reality that batteries are still used and eventually discarded.

Methods: In this paper, the authors emphasise the significance of power consumption in battery powered devices. To be able to monitor devices power consumption, one of the measurable parameters is current. When users know the exact current consumption, they can decrease it by polishing the program or tweaking the duty cycle, making radio transmit less data or less frequently, thus decreasing overall power draw.

Results: In order to simplify current consumption monitoring, the authors have developed a testbed facility that provides real-time current consumption measurements, which may be used to enhance the duty cycle and battery life of the aforementioned devices.

Conclusions: While minimising total current consumption is a great way to extend the battery life and, thus, the carbon footprint, the primary culprit in the Internet of Things is the radio communications. This transmission is the primary source of current consumption. By determining the exact amount of current drawn during transmission and adjusting it, users can significantly extend battery life.

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Keywords

IoT, TestBed, Current consumption, Realtime, Carbon Footprint, WSN, Measurement

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Plain language summary

When you look at everyday life, you can see that almost everyone uses or at least comes into contact with the Internet of Things (IoT) or wireless sensor network (WSN) technologies at some point. Seeing how fast these devices are becoming more popular and how many there are, the authors decided to bring attention to the problem of the carbon footprint these devices are creating. By introducing the second version of their testbed facility, the authors talk about how important it is to measure the amount of current used in real time for the Internet of Things and wireless sensor network devices during their development phase. When the developers know exactly how much current their product is using, they can improve their performance, make the batteries last longer, and in turn reduce their carbon footprint. In the article, the authors talk about the requirements for the new testbed facility and how they tested and chose the necessary components to find the ones that are needed.

Introduction

The reduction of the electrical energy consumption to extend battery life of wireless devices is one of the main challenges for modern Internet of Things (IoT) systems, which are typically represented as a combination of a wireless sensor network (WSN) and a data processing block^{1,2}. The total energy consumption of wireless IoT devices is affected by multiple complex factors: (i) the electrical design of the device³, (ii) the efficiency of the firmware⁴, (iii) duty cycle of sensor node activity⁵, (iv) duty cycle of the wireless radio⁵, (v) disturbances and interference from other devices deployed in the same environment⁶, (vi) wireless packet collisions⁷ and other, which are often noticed only after the deployment of IoT devices.

Because of the complexity of aforementioned factors the theoretical estimation of energy consumption in real environments is exceedingly complicated, but the empirical evaluation of these factors during the development phase is encumbered by the fact that IoT devices are frequently deployed in situations where they are not accessible and permanent connection to the power grid is not possible^{8,9}, such as environmental or agricultural monitoring¹⁰⁻¹². This can be solved by combining a system for electrical energy consumption monitoring and a wireless IoT testbed, that could be deployed in real environment for testing of different operating modes.

This paper describes the architecture and electrical design of a current consumption monitoring solution for the implementation in the “EDI TestBed”, a testbed facility developed in the “EDI” - Institute of Electronics and Computer Science, Riga, Latvia, further referred to as TestBed V1. This work is build upon the previous iteration of testbed (TestBed V1), which consists of: (i) software controlled power management unit (PMU), (ii) digital voltmeter circuit, (iii) current consumption measurement system, and (iiii) full access remote control of the device under test (DUT).

Additionally, several lessons learned describing improvements and requirements for the next iteration of EDI TestBed, further referred as TestBed V2, is provided.

Related work

Several current measurement systems suitable for IoT applications have been identified and described. First of all we will describe the testbed facility EDI TestBed developed by Institute of Electronics and Computer Science, in this article referred as TestBed, is extensively described in the available literature, general description is given by Ruskuls *et al.*¹³, details about the current consumption measuring system are described by Lapsa *et al.*³, furthermore Judvaitis *et al.*¹⁴ provides the back-end system overview and their technical implementation, Salmins *et al.*¹⁵ provides an overview of the mobility aspect and together with the future development plans and DevOps integration described by Judvaitis *et al.*¹⁶ this forms the core of TestBed. Practical use cases and usage evaluation is provided by Judvaitis *et al.*¹⁷, Elkenawy and Judvaitis¹⁸.

TestBed V1^{3,13} was good at energy consumption monitoring, but nowadays it has become obsolete, as limitations of range and accuracy are increasing with a power technologies evolution and expansion of IoT systems. TestBed energy consumption monitoring subsystems operates as follows:

- Configurable power supply can be managed to produce constant voltage in range from 0.78V to 4.7V by using adjustable Low-dropout (LDO) voltage regulator;
- Current consumption monitoring system range and accuracy depends on chosen ammeter circuit that acts as a double range shunt ammeter with the ability to choose the range by switching shunt value between 10Ω and 0.82Ω. The output voltage value is captured by 16-bit 500kHz analog-to-digital converter (ADC) and interpreted as a current value by knowing shunt resistor value. Measured current range is between 0.1μA – 100mA with a maximum relative error of 0.4%

There are multiple versions of current measurement systems available for IoT systems. Although most of them lack one or more features that are available and ready to use in TestBed.

SPOT - scalable power observation tool¹⁹, represents a low-cost (< 25\$) device for testing low power IoT nodes. It measures current consumption using single shunt ammeter channel. Despite the cost, SPOT has an impressive sampling frequency value for 1M Hz and good current sense accuracy below 1μA that makes it possible to accurately calculate overall energy consumption value. But SPOT still has two major disadvantages:

- It doesn't have a built-in power management unit.
- Current measurement range is only up to 40mA that makes it useless for high current devices testing.

The Raspberry Pi compatible energy measurement platform for wireless IoT devices “EMPIOT”²⁰, just like TestBed, works using shunt ammeter approach. The main purpose of this platform is energy consumption testing for each node of an IoT system. The compatibility of EMPIOT with the Raspberry Pi platform allows it to design a wide range of experimental IoT systems. The shortcoming of this system accuracy - 0.1mA.

SANDBed^{21,22} is the wireless sensor and actuator network (WSAN) development system which has a testbed approach with more use cases than regular current consumption logger. As with all testbed functions it has same issues caused by the compromises between price, functionality, and quality. This system has an unusual current range switching solution, it switches between three current ranges instead of common single or double range solution: 100mA, 200mA, 500mA. But this solution also has a lot of limitations namely the limited current measurement accuracy, which equals to 2% and maximum sampling frequency value - 400kHz;

RocketLogger^{23,24}, is an open-source energy harvesting logger. Portability allows to use it for IoT system design. RocketLogger has significant advantage to all aforementioned solutions – it’s current measurement accuracy, it is obtained by using double current measurement range with a different ammeter technique for each channel.

- Shunt ammeter for a high current range (2mA – 500mA) with a shunt value 50mΩ
- Feedback ammeter for a low current range (10nA – 2mA) with a feedback resistance 680Ω

For low current circuits, the measurement accuracy is 0.03% + 4nA, and for high current circuit, it is 0.09% + 3μA. Rocketlogger has a in-built configurable PMU with range from -5V to +5V and digital voltmeter with 5.5V range and 0.02% + 13μV accuracy that allows users to calculate consumed energy

using voltage supply from both RocketLogger and external source.

Despite all of its advantages, Rocketlogger has too low a sampling frequency to calculate communication device energy consumption per bit, this limitation comes from 64kHz ADC.

While TestBed V2 development previous experience and related works were taken into account to release non-compromised energy harvesting measurement system with a wide measurement range, high accuracy, and fast sampling frequency to allow wide IoT system type testing.

Architecture

EDI TestBed has been in development for some time now¹³, and throughout the years has been improved in a numerous ways^{3,14-18}. One of the key functions of TestBed has always been energy consumption monitoring, and this function has been improved in several iterations. While the base idea stays the same, there are several improvements to functionality by increasing the resolution and reliability of TestBed energy consumption measurement system.

Figure 1 depicts the basic functionality of the TestBed V1 current measurement system. Current meter circuitry uses shunt ammeter approach³ described in detail in Section.

While there are other available current measurement methods^{25,26}, this was chosen due to its affordability and ease of use, as the number of components required to accomplish the desired outcome is relatively modest.

The TestBed V1 current measurement scale is set from 100nA up to 100mA. The goal was to measure the consumed current during the nodes duty cycle, which includes sleep and active mode. During the sleep phase, current consumption

Figure 1. Basic block diagram of TestBed V1 current measurement circuit.

is measured in μA while during the active phase, which involves sensor data gathering and radio communications, current consumption can increase and is measured in mA . To be able to measure the current in a range so wide, there were two different precise resistors R_{sense} placed in series with the device under test (DUT) (R_{load}). The actual resistor used is selected based on the actual current consumed.

The desired power supply for the DUT is +5V DC, which can be provided by an external power supply or a Universal Serial Bus (USB) 2.0 connection from a computer. To protect the computer's USB controller, electrostatic discharge (ESD) protection diodes were fitted at the inputs of both power supply lines. The ESD protection diode changes the available voltage supply by reducing the source voltage by 0.5V. According to the USB 2.0 specification²⁷, high-powered hub port voltage ranges from 4.75V to 5.25V, while low-powered hub port voltage ranges from 4.4V to 5.25V. Thus, the absolute worst-case scenario that is acceptable is if the hub's voltage drops to 4.4V, at which point, according to USB specification²⁷, only low-power functions can operate. Although reducing input voltage by 0.5 volts at input seems high, it is within acceptable range as it leaves 4.5V to operate with.

The data sampling frequency in TestBed V1 is only 12.75kHz. Due to the maximum reading frequency of 6,375 kHz according to the Nyquist theorem, this criterion is very imitating for use of the TestBed V1 for IoT applications.

$$f_N = \frac{f_s}{2} \quad (1)$$

where

f_N - Nyquist frequency that represents as a maximum reading frequency,

f_s - bandwidth of the signal.

In this regard, the TestBed V2 maximum reading frequency increased to 500kHz with 1MHz sampling frequency.

The TestBed V1 has two different variants: (i) Stationary¹³, and (ii) mobile¹⁵. A stationary testbed is placed throughout the EDI building and is supposed to be used only in laboratory conditions, see [Figure 2](#). While the mobile testbed has Ingress Protection (IP) rating 54 enabled enclosure and is meant to be used outside see [Figure 3](#).

Practical lessons learned from original EDI TestBed

At the time of development, current consumption above 100mA for a WSN node was considered too high, but recently it has become more common to get devices with current consumption much higher than 100mA. For this reason, the 100mA range is defined as a shortcoming and the authors aim to increase it in the latest revision. In addition, the lowest readable current has a 100nA value, this value also has to be improved. For example, the STM32L476xx Microcontroller (MCU) in ultra low power mode can consume as little as 30nA of current²⁸.

Figure 2. Stationary TestBed workstation.

Figure 3. Mobile TestBed V1 workstation.

ESD protection diodes protect the power supply but does reduce the input by around 0.5V. While, according to USB 2.0 specification²⁷, this is within the acceptable range, it makes the system provide power only to low-power functions. While utilising TestBed V1, we observed that in some instances, the DUT did not function properly, rebooting at, what appeared to be, random intervals or failing to turn on at all. Later, we discovered that there were extra 200 – 400mV voltage drops along the cables we used, which caused our DUTs to reboot when more power was required or not power up at all when the voltage losses were bigger. In later stages of development, we were able to replace our cables and improve power reliability³.

The original current measurement system is suppressed by the small voltage spectrum. While it works on all USB 2.0 devices, it does exclude some USB 3.x devices and different automotive and urban devices. At the time of creation, 5V systems were chosen due to the USB standard, but a closer study reveals that the power supply range should be changed, widening the available spectrum from 3.3V to 15V to expand

support for additional devices, as common IoT hardware has similar power requirements²⁹. In addition Power over Ethernet (PoE) has been increasingly used in home security and has been used in other fields³⁰.

Requirements

This section describes the set requirements for the new TestBed V2, taking into account the latest research and lessons learned from TestBed V1.

Functional requirements:

Functional requirements for the new TestBed V2 describes basic functionality of what the system is supposed to do and its parameters. While we do describe the whole system, the main premise is the current consumption measurement system.

PMU requirements:

- The TestBed V2 adapter provides the DUT with a controlled voltage source; This indicates that the voltage input to the DUT is precise and stable.
- The TestBed V2 adapter can simulate battery charging and discharging;

This requirement remains the same as in the TestBed V1, so that the user may see what to expect from a device as the battery voltage drops by simulating battery discharge.

- The TestBed V2 adapter can be powered by a variety of external power sources;

If the TestBed V2 adapter can only be supplied by grid power, this can be troublesome, hence additional power supply choices, such as PoE, battery, and external power adapter, must be available.

- To power the TestBed V2 adapter multiple power sources can be used simultaneously;

This need is precautionary, so that when the TestBed V2 adapter is simultaneously attached to battery and external power supply, there are no conflicts.

- The TestBed V2 adapter can measure the DUT current consumption in real time.

Connectivity requirements.

Certain criteria have been established to improve TestBed V2 connectivity with DUT. While using TestBed V1, we realized that various wired and wireless connection protocols would be desirable in addition to the USB serial communication option.

- The TestBed V2 adapter uses standardised wired and wireless digital interfaces to communicate with the DUT and the testbed server;

To reduce the likelihood of user error, communication must be established in accordance with specific standards, such as supplying the USB 2.0 Type A connector with only 5V DC. In addition, wireless connectivity is being added between the TestBed V2

adapter and the DUT. All employed communication protocols and interfaces must adhere to predetermined standards.

- The device can be used as a standalone device.

The TestBed V2 adapter consists of numerous modules, such as the power supply and current measuring module. Each of them should be capable of functioning independently. The user should be able to utilize the current measurement module without the TestBed V2 power source, instead powering it directly from a personal computer or laboratory desktop power supply.

Debugging interface requirements.

Requirements for DUT debugging during development life cycle. There are numerous debugging methods, and their respective requirements for successful and straightforward debugging are outlined here.

- Debug and update DUT firmware remotely;

Important characteristics of testbeds include the capacity to remotely update and reprogram the DUT. This useful feature permits the simultaneous reprogramming of many DUTs.

- Reset the DUT operation remotely;

This requirement is useful if the DUT has crashed and is unresponsive, in which case a physical reset must be performed. In most circumstances, this is accomplished via a push button or switch on the DUT, but in our scenario, the reset must be toggled remotely.

- Serial communication channel between the DUT and a remote client/device;

A DUT has to appear as a serial communication device, as a seamless pass-through of the chosen communication channel, this helps with development, as from the clients perspective the DUT is directly connected to clients development platform.

- Logging capability for the DUT.

A complete log file of data input and output from DUT.

Casing requirements.

The TestBed V2 adapter has safety mechanisms for protecting its hardware and connected DUT's in dangerous operational conditions.

IP 54 is the most common rating for devices and is the easiest to achieve, the original TestBed already achieved this IP rating. But it only protects the device from dust and splashing water³¹. If the TestBed V2 should be used in a more moist environment, for example a swamp, a lakeside or in a strong rain, than the rating must be up to IP 57. The protection from dust stays the same, but in addition to that we are increasing protection from being submerged in water up to 1m in depth. In addition, dangerous operational conditions also includes protection from overheating.

Operational requirements

The requirements on how and in what conditions the system is supposed to operate is described further. From theoretical point of view the requirements related to the current consumption measurement of Internet of Things devices have increased recently, the most demanding hardware can achieve as low as $0.03\mu A$ current consumption in most aggressive current saving mode³². On the other hand, the narrow Band Internet of Things devices can consume up to $280mA$ ³³. The voltage of some of the mentioned Internet of Things devices can go from $3.3V$ up to as high as $15V$ ³⁴. Based on the latest IoT devices available on the market we have set a demanding **list of requirements for the PMU**:

- Output current range up to 1A
- Output voltage range 0V - 34V
- Current measurement range 2nA - 3A
- Current measurement frequency 1MHz
- Current measurement accuracy 100pA

Power supply unit architecture

The TestBed V2 is intended to run from a number of power sources, including POE up to 100W, USB type-C with power delivery support up to 100W, and a barrel jack connector: voltage range of 4.5V to 36V

TestBed V2 can also be utilised as a power supply for connected DUT *via* TestBed Adapter. Thus, TestBed V2 PSU is a universal power supply with an intuitive interface, as it accepts a range of input power sources and prepares them for DUT.

As the TestBed is designed to represent a wide range of operational conditions, authors have distributed the TestBed adapters throughout the EDI main building, including outdoors. TestBed V2 offers control over output voltage and output current, as well as the “stable mode” that attempts to adjust as much as possible for fluctuations in current and voltage. The output voltage and current of the power supply will depend on the power supply topology selected for the TestBed.

High current measurement mode

For high current range measurements we are still using a shunt ammeter circuit see [Figure 4](#). This method measures gained voltage across a shunt resistor. And the current (I) measurement is obtained by dividing this voltage drop measurement (V_{DROP}) with the known value of the resistor (R_S).

$$I = V_{DROP} / R_S \quad (2)$$

R_S is connected in series with a DUT that introduces a voltage drop error to the circuit. The weak point of this circuit can show up if R_S is too high compared with a load impedance. So shunt resistance should be as low as possible, to reduce voltage drop across it. For our implementation we have chosen a $50m\Omega$ resistor as a shunt resistor as it will create only $150mV$ drop if there is $3A$ load thru measuring circuit, this is specified upper limit of current measurement. Also $50m\Omega$ resistor provides capability to theoretically measure current from $1nA$ up to $3A$ using 32bit ADC if there is no noise but in real world its not possible due noise and voltage drift in whole measuring circuit. Calculations for this $50m\Omega$ resistor was done using spreadsheet for visually providing information about ranges, voltage drop and current capability, spreadsheet is in supplementary data³⁵ in the *Shunt-and-gain-calculations.xlsx* file.

Low current measurement mode

In the low current architecture a feedback ammeter technique is used [4](#). The feedback ammeter’s most significant difference is smaller voltage drop (V_{DROP}), that makes it possible to measure smaller current changes with smaller error rate. The current (I) measurement is obtained by dividing output voltage (V_O) with known shunt resistance (R_S)

$$I = V_O / R_S \quad (3)$$

By utilising operational amplifier its also possible to get readings faster than using shunt ammeter measuring due to nature of voltage settling across resistor, if it is needed to measure small current by using shut ammeter method then shunt resistor (RS) nominal must be high, and that with capacitance form wiring makes large settling time for such circuit.

Figure 4. Shunt ammeter vs feedback ammeter.

Simulation

During TestBed V2 development phase many main component simulations and evaluations were done, these simulations were performed to reduce prototyping iterations and to gain a deeper understanding of how the integrated circuit(IC) will perform in conjunction with other electrical components. The described simulations are published in supplementary data³⁵ in the *Simulations* folder. The circuit simulations for the most important parts of the developed adapter, with the respective file name in brackets, are as follows: (i) main power converter, TestBed V2 power supply part responsible for DUT power, multi power input rail part(*testbed_ideal_diode file*), “over the top” operational amplifier functionality(*opamp_adc_buf file*) and low current feedback amperemeter part(*feedback_amp file*).

TestBed V2’s main power part was simulated due need of checking for noise, “Voltage for Input-to-Output Control” and how positive and negative power rails will work. This consisted of buck-boost converter LT8210³⁶ *testbed_main_bb_positive_negative file* which is used to adjust voltage accordingly from one of used input rails. Power is regulated accordingly to next power paths component - LDO LT3045-1³⁷, this is achieved by utilising special LT3045-1 functionality “Voltage for Input-to-Output Control” (VIOC) witch controls converter before LDO so that LDO doesn’t need to deal with huge voltage difference between input and output of it as LDO by its principle converts voltage difference in heat, furthermore this reduced whole system power and heat waste. The LDO choice was also based on noise parameter as chosen LDO also has very low noise in output. As this part is also responsive for negative power rail there is another voltage converter³⁸ witch is in inverter mode to produce negative voltage from positive rail. On the negative voltage circuit buck-boost converter was also used together with negative voltage LDO³⁹ using the VIOC feature, also to reduce heat and power waste in system. Resulting circuit produces positive and negative voltage rails that further is used in measurement circuits as they provide very low noise due design and component choices.

During development and simulation process for DUT power supply *testbed_psu_filter file* a simple approach was chosen, using LT3081⁴⁰ which can be regulated from Digital to Analogue converter(DAC). DAC wasn’t included is simulation as simulation as it wasn’t necessary. Also LDO should have the potential to regulate the voltage from 0 to input rail voltage. In simulation regarding this part protection against scenario where DAC could provide higher voltage than power supply voltage was included using Over the top operational amplifier LT6015⁴¹. In case if DUT should have very stable voltage output there is implemented capacitor filter for power rail fluctuation if needed. For the TestBed V2 input power rails there was a need to check and simulate if system could be powered from different power paths simultaneously not damaging device itself and also not damaging the power rails. Such option was simulated with so called ideal diode LTC4359⁴² which instead of real diodes uses mosfets to turn on or off power

rails according to input rail state. For testing purposes a simulation was created where operational amplifier LT6015 characteristics were tested together with the earlier mentioned over the top feature. Another simulation was created for low current measurement circuit with ultra low noise operational amplifier ADA4522⁴³ whose output was fed in ADC driver LTC6363⁴⁴.

Evaluation and results

In this section authors describe how they developed the TestBed V2 according to requirements and lessons learned from TestBed V1. A brief introduction to the system as a whole is given, with the main emphasis on current measurement system.

The important concept that was kept in mind during the development of the TestBed V2 was versatility and as such diverse supply voltages and operation conditions were the primary features that were maximised.

TestBed V1 utilises a “multi-processor for multi-function” approach¹³, which results in an exponential increase in complexity with each new feature. In contrast, the new TestBed V2 architecture is planned to utilise a single microprocessor that is powerful enough to perform data processing and support all required TestBed V2 features, increasing the data processing speed and streamlining the system development. To develop TestBed V2 current measurement system we took inspiration from the RocketLogger architecture Described in Section, which enables measurements in two ranges: (i) ultra-low current consumption measurement for sleep mode performance study and (ii) normal operating mode for active state analysis. This approach gives the ability to seamlessly switch between two modes, which gives uninterrupted data to user about the DUT’s current consumption. This means that there is no need to manually switch the current measurement mode while DUT is in sleep or active mode. The two different current measurement modes utilise two different current measurement techniques: Shunt ammeter - for a high current range, and feedback ammeter for a low current range.

The TestBed V2 adapter inherits the same paradigms as the TestBed V1 itself . The adapter’s primary objective is versatility and with this in mind, the primary focus has to be on developing user-friendly software for TestBed V2 adapter, which works as a bridge between the TestBed V2 infrastructure and the DUT. The DUT can be operated *via* the TestBed V2 adapter either as a USB device or as an independent device linked *via* a terminal block. If the USB topology is employed, it is possible to connect with the DUT *via* the TestBed V2 adapter using the built-in USB hub or to move the DUT to an independent USB port using pass-thru mode, where another device communicates with the DUT.

Hardware choices

In the initial phase of development we reduced the number of available ADC’s and MCU’s that are compatible with our requirements Described in Section by looking at their theoretical characteristics. Later we built a breakout boards with chosen

ADC's and operational/instrumental amplifier to test real world performance, to see if by some means the said theoretical performance, like sample frequency in conjunction with test MCU's and single board computers (SBC) e.g. Raspberry PI, RockPI, could not be achieved.

ADC for current measurement system was chosen to fulfil predefined requirements but also considering MCU capabilities to be reasonable. As potential candidates the LTC2335-18⁴⁵ and LTC2500-32⁴⁶ were chosen. LTC2335-18 was considered due 1MHz data acquisition speed for measurements, 8 channel multiplex for flexibility and possible design simplicity, 18bit sampling resolution and SoftSpan feature. SoftSpan enables each output range to be configured via software individually. This can also reduce the complexity of the Printed Circuit Board (PCB). LTC2500-32 on the other hand was also chosen due 1MHz data acquisition speed and 32bit precision filtered output capabilities. Both ADC supported 100MHz SPI data transfer frequency that could be sufficient to manage data transfer frequency of 1MHz.

As the TestBed V1 was multi-processor system, we decided to redesign everything to be more centred but with more

powerful microprocessor. The options were narrowed down to single board computers that could run Linux distribution and had good documentation, (i) Raspberry Pi 4⁴⁷, (ii) Hardkernel Odroid C4⁴⁸, (iii) Radxa RockPi 4⁴⁹ and Nvidia Jetson Nano⁵⁰. At the end Nvidia Jetson Nano was chosen due to the included Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) cores, that offer possibilities to develop machine learning algorithms and systems powered by artificial intelligence.

Printed circuit board

From acquired requirements authors designed a six layer PCB with "Altium Designer" (industry standard for PCB Design)⁵¹, with open source alternatives available, like "KiCad"⁵², including power supply unit as-well as current measurement system as a single board unit. The necessity to migrate from two layer PCB of TestBed V1 to six layers on TestBed V2, was the increased complexity of new PCB. This PCB is designed to interface with Jetson Nano and act as a bridge between both DUT and Jetson Nano. In Figure 5 is seen the 3D design of said PCB designed with "Autodesk Fusion 360"⁵³ software, with open source alternatives available, like "Blender"⁵⁴ or "FreeCad"⁵⁵.

Casing

First sketch of TestBed V2 design was made on a piece of paper see Figure 6. In the design there can be seen that the enclosure is supposed to act as a passive cooling system for the whole device, therefore improving the thermals and IP rating, because there are no holes for air cooling. All of the necessary ports are routed to the side and are meant to be sealed. To improve the radio coverage the antennas are pulled out of the enclosure, so that no metal enclosure would harm the radio reception.

Table 1. ADC parameters.

Parameter	LTC2335-18	LTC2500-32
Data transfer frequency	1MHz	1MHz
Channels	8	1
Resolution	18	32
Data transfer frequency	100 MHz	100 MHz

Figure 5. TestBed V2 Printed Circuit Board 3D design.

The next step was to use 3D computer-aided design (CAD) software to design a suitable enclosure for TestBed V2, taking into account the PCB that had been designed, see Figure 5, and the fact that the first prototype will be 3D printed using ABS Plastic. There are only TestBed V2 components included inside the enclosure at this stage - power supply, current consumption monitoring system and central processing unit, which is the Nvidia Jetson Nano⁵⁰ developer kit, see Figure 7. As in the sketch all of connectors are pulled to the side of enclosure. As this enclosure is supposed to be plastic, it is impossible to cool the system using it as a housing, so one side of the enclosure has been designed so that air could flow freely cooling the Jetson Nano and other components on the board. To increase the airflow additional cooling fan is attached and fitted to one of the sides see Figure 7.

To test both ADC's 1 in question authors set up a test bench where both ADC's were mounted on breakout boards with additional components as per both ADC's datasheets and wiring underneath for communication and data acquisition.⁸ During testing of 32bit ADC there were multiple hardware and software iterations during selecting adequate MCU and software combination, the software used in the tests is added as additional data to this publication³⁵. The first tests were performed on Arduino DUO platform using SAM3X8E 32bit ARM Cortex M3 MCU. Those tests were for proof of concept to see if its possible to acquire any data and how does the ADC perform. During testing ADC performance and communication we also used DSLogic U3Pro16 logic analyser MCU where the clock source and logic analyser was used as the data acquisition device. Only proof of concept data was captured as

Figure 6. "TestBed V2" visual sketch.

Figure 7. "TestBed v2" prototype 3D designed enclosure.

screenshots during XM1000 mote bootup stage via low speed USB connection.⁹

During testing and while choosing the final platform for ADC communication, there also were tests on RockPI and Raspberry PI platforms. Authors tested maximum data acquisition speed from ADC using SPI protocol and hardware

connection between ADC and test platform. Additionally to SPI protocol hardware pinout there were used ADC specific trigger pins as BUSY, CLOCK, DRL to be aware of ADC state. State of ADC was important as as during ADC sampling there should not be data reading as it renders ADC sample invalid. BUSY signal meant that ADC is in sampling phase, CLOCK signal additional to SPI clock signal was used as ADC sampling

Figure 8. Testing breakout board.

Figure 9. Captured proof of concept data³⁵.

start signal and DRL signal was used as flag to determinate available data on ADC for reading. From platform side of tests this was done by utilising kernel module functionality to test platform capability of driving ADC and receiving data streams, used test code is published in supplementary data³⁵ in the *Testbed VI SBC modules* folder. Unfortunately it was not possible to reliably utilise them even in real time kernel, as the maximum possible frequency of data would be only ~ 300 kHz on ADC not considering actual data reading. ADC sampling takes around ~ 600ns, while less than 400ns are required to establish the SPI data connection, retrieve data, and prepare for the next transfer. If data is read during an ADC sample cycle, it becomes invalid due to SPI transmission and mixed data stored in the memory buffer of the ADC. In addition, at these sample frequencies and with the SBC continuously triggering for data read, since the ADC triggers an interrupt signal on the SBC for data transfer, the SBC became unusable and unresponsive for any other job. During these tests, the authors decided to discard the concept of using any SBC to communicate directly with ADC from the MCU.

During researching of other available data reading options from ADC authors tested different MCU and SBC options like Arduino DUE core board.

Using this “Arduino DUE core” board in conjunction with ADC breakout board⁸ by utilising same data acquisition and ADC triggering methods as earlier mentioned with SBC’s except for kernel module part as its not applicable to test MCU it was possible to acquire data with a sample frequency of 300kHz not only triggering as it was with SBC’s. Additionally it was also possible to explore each ADC features such as data averaging and filtering in case of 32 bit ADC by utilising second SPI data channel of ADC, all of features is available in ADC datasheet⁴⁶ and commented on test code that is published in supplementary data³⁵ in the *Testbed VI due core test* folder. However, given the output capabilities of chosen ADC and requirements described in Section , this sample frequency was insufficient. The MCU board based on an STM32H743VIT6 was the next board evaluated, used test code is published in supplementary data³⁵ in the *STM32H743 CubeMX test* folder. Additionally to same testing scheme as it was done with “Arduino DUE core” board there was used option to ignore data ready flags, but instead generate clock for triggering ADC sampling and rely on manufacture defined timing constrains of ADC, so that after triggering ADC sample wait in idle at least 630ns and then without reading any data ready flag assume that data has been captured and use DMA to offload Central Processing Unit (CPU) with direct registry writing and reading to further offload CPU processing cycles, the authors were able to achieve with this schheme a sample frequency above 900kHz. Research revealed that this was one of the most powerful MCU’s on the market at the time in terms of MCU clock speed, pin count, and implementation, so the decision was made to stick with this type of MCU that was a little bit more powerful so that it could perform not only data acquisition but also other tasks, like DUT power supply management and data processing for

host system over USB. MCU developed by STMicroelectronics were used after exhaustive research into quicker and more accessible computer platforms. As its clock frequency was 480MHz, GPIO frequency was also significantly increased.

Discussion

Even though the EDI TestBed V2 is not quite complete, we were able to collect sufficient data³⁵ to verify that we are moving in the correct direction. In future iterations, we intend to isolate the current measurement device and the power supply unit onto different PCBs. When designing both of them, we noticed that the majority of components and functionality required for the power supply unit are already populated on the current consumption PCB, therefore the decision was made to integrate them onto a single PCB for prototyping and usability considerations.

The EDI TestBed v2 could be utilised to enhance current wireless networks as well as for the creation of new ones. Our current consumption measuring system can identify the highest consumers and time periods, allowing users to utilise the data as they see fit. For instance, one could determine that it is preferable to use an additional ULP MCU in addition to the main MCU, so that the main MCU can be shut down for the duration of sleep, or that there is no need, since the MCU used in the system has a superior sleep mode than the ULP MCU, and waking the MCU can actually decrease the battery’s lifetime. Due to the variety of use cases, these findings may vary, for instance, there may be varying needs for the frequency of sensor readings, resulting in variations in duty cycle.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

Extended data

Zenodo: Supplementary data for Precise realtime current consumption measurement in IoT TestBed publication. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7417349> by Balass *et al.*³⁵

This project contains the following extended data:

- Simulations (folder containing simulations of circuits of TestBed V2)
- STM32H743 CubeMX test (folder containing code)
- Testbed due core test (folder containing code)
- Testbed SBC modules (folder containing code)
- Shunt-and-gain-calculations.xlsx (Data for gain and size of shunt resistor)

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Zero “No rights reserved” data waiver \(CC0 1.0 Public domain dedication\)](#).

References

1. Manrique JA, Rueda-Rueda JS, Portocarrero JMT: **Contrasting internet of things and wireless sensor network from a conceptual overview.** In: *2016 IEEE international conference on Internet of Things (IThings) and IEEE green computing and communications (GreenCom) and IEEE cyber, physical and social computing (CPSCom) and IEEE smart data (SmartData)*. IEEE, 2016; 252–257. [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Zhao S, Rengasamy PV, Zhang H, et al.: **Understanding energy efficiency in iot app executions.** In: *2019 IEEE 39th international conference on distributed computing systems (ICDCS)*. IEEE, 2019; 742–755. [Publisher Full Text](#)
3. Lapsa D, Balass R, Judvaitis J, et al.: **Measurement of current consumption in a wireless sensor network testbed.** In: *2017 25th Telecommunication Forum (TELFOR)*. 2017; 1–4. [Publisher Full Text](#)
4. Simunic T, Benini L, De Micheli G, et al.: **Source code optimization and profiling of energy consumption in embedded systems.** In: *Proceedings 13th International Symposium on System Synthesis*. IEEE, 2000; 193–198. [Publisher Full Text](#)
5. Kozłowski A, Sosnowski J: **Energy efficiency trade-off between duty-cycling and wake-up radio techniques in iot networks.** *Wireless Pers Commun*. 2019; **107**(4): 1951–1971. [Publisher Full Text](#)
6. Ancans A, Ormanis J, Cacus R, et al.: **Bluetooth low energy throughput in densely deployed radio environment.** In: *2019 23rd International Conference Electronics*. 2019; 1–5. [Publisher Full Text](#)
7. Zhou G, He T, Stankovic JA, et al.: **Rid: Radio interference detection in wireless sensor networks.** In: *Proceedings IEEE 24th Annual Joint Conference of the IEEE Computer and Communications Societies*. IEEE, 2005; **2**: 891–901. [Publisher Full Text](#)
8. Talavera JM, Tobón LE, Gómez JA, et al.: **Review of IoT applications in agro-industrial and environmental fields.** *Comput Electron Agr*. 2017; **142**: 283–297. [Publisher Full Text](#)
9. Judvaitis J, Mednis A, Abolins V, et al.: **Classification of actual sensor network deployments in research studies from 2013 to 2017.** *Data*. 2020; **5**(4): 93. [Publisher Full Text](#)
10. Elsts A, Balass R, Judvaitis J, et al.: **Sad: wireless sensor network system for microclimate monitoring in precision agriculture.** In: *Proceedings of the 5-th international scientific conference Applied information and communication technologies (AICT 2012)*. 2012; 271–281. [Reference Source](#)
11. Zabasta A, Kunicina N, Vitols K, et al.: **Low-power wireless sensor network system for early diagnostic of subacute rumen acidosis in cows.** In: *2019 IEEE 7th IEEE Workshop on Advances in Information, Electronic and Electrical Engineering (AIEEE)*. IEEE, 2019; 1–6. [Publisher Full Text](#)
12. Zabasta A, Kunicina N, Grunde U, et al.: **Implementation of iot concept for early diagnostic of subacute rumen acidosis in cows.** In: *2020 9th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing (MECO)*. IEEE, 2020; 1–4. [Publisher Full Text](#)
13. Ruskuls R, Lapsa D, Selavo L: **Edi wsn testbed: Multifunctional, 3d wireless sensor network testbed.** In: *2015 Advances in Wireless and Optical Communications (RTUWO)*. IEEE, 2015; 50–53. [Publisher Full Text](#)
14. Judvaitis J, Salmins A, Nesenbergs K: **Network data traffic management inside a testbed.** In: *2016 Advances in Wireless and Optical Communications (RTUWO)*. IEEE, 2016; 152–155. [Publisher Full Text](#)
15. Salmins A, Judvaitis J, Balass R, et al.: **Mobile wireless sensor network testbed.** In: *2017 25th Telecommunication Forum (TELFOR)*. IEEE, 2017; 1–4. [Publisher Full Text](#)
16. Judvaitis J, Nesenbergs K, Balass R, et al.: **Challenges of devops ready iot testbed.** In: *MDE4IoT/ModComp@MoDELS*. 2019. [Reference Source](#)
17. Judvaitis J, Balass R, Greitans M: **Mobile iot-edge-cloud continuum based and devops enabled software framework.** *J Sens Actuator Netw*. 2021; **10**(4): 62. [Publisher Full Text](#)
18. Elkenawy A, Judvaitis J: **Transmission power influence on wsn-based indoor localization efficiency.** *Sensors (Basel)*. 2022; **22**(11): 4154. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
19. Jiang X, Dutta P, Culler D, et al.: **Micro power meter for energy monitoring of wireless sensor networks at scale.** In: *2007 6th International Symposium on Information Processing in Sensor Networks*. IEEE, 2007; 186–195. [Publisher Full Text](#)
20. Dezfouli B, Amirtharaj I, Chelsey Li CC: **Empiot: An energy measurement platform for wireless iot devices.** *J Netw Comput Appl*. 2018; **121**: 135–148. [Publisher Full Text](#)
21. Hergenröder A, Horneber J, Wilke J: **Sandbed: A wsan testbed for network management and energy monitoring.** Hamburg, Germany, 2009. [Reference Source](#)
22. Hergenröder A, Horneber J, Meier D, et al.: **Demo abstract: Distributed energy measurements in wireless sensor networks.** In: *7th ACM Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems (SenSys)*; Berkeley, California, USA November 4-6, 2009. 2009; **299**. [Publisher Full Text](#)
23. Sigrist L, Gomez A, Lim R, et al.: **Measurement and validation of energy harvesting iot devices.** In: *Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE)*, 2017. IEEE, 2017; 1159–1164. [Publisher Full Text](#)
24. Sigrist L, Gomez A, Lim R, et al.: **Rocketlogger: Mobile power logger for prototyping iot devices: Demo abstract.** *Proceedings of the 14th ACM Conference on Embedded Network Sensor Systems CD-ROM*. 2016; 288–289. [Publisher Full Text](#)
25. **Low Level Measurements Handbook.** 6th. Chapter. 2004; **6**: 54–57.
26. Forghani-Zadeh HP, Rincon-Mora GA: **Current-sensing techniques for dc-dc converters.** In: *Circuits and Systems, 2002. MWSCAS-2002. The 2002 45th Midwest Symposium on*. IEEE, 2002; **2**: II-II. [Publisher Full Text](#)
27. **Universal serial bus specification revision 2.0.** Accessed: 2022-20-07. [Reference Source](#)
28. **Stm microelectronics stm32l476xx datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-21-07. [Reference Source](#)
29. Singh D, Sandhu A, Thakur AS, et al.: **An overview of iot hardware development platforms.** 08 2020. [Reference Source](#)
30. Minoli D, Sohraby K, Occhiogrosso B: **Iot considerations, requirements, and architectures for smart buildings—energy optimization and next-generation building management systems.** *IEEE Internet Things J*. 2017; **4**(1): 269–283. [Publisher Full Text](#)
31. **Ingress protection ratings by international electrotechnical commission.** Accessed: 2022-25-07. [Reference Source](#)
32. STMicroelectronics: **Stm32wlex wireless mcus with lora support.** 2021; [accessed September 13, 2021]. [Reference Source](#)
33. Quectel Wireless Solutions: **Quectel-bc95 specification.** 2020; [accessed September 13, 2021]. [Reference Source](#)
34. Singh D, Sandhu A, Thakur AS, et al.: **An overview of iot hardware development platforms.** *Int J Emerg Techn*. 2020. [Reference Source](#)
35. Balass R, Medvedevs V, Mackus AI, et al.: **Supplementary data for Precise realtime current consumption measurement in IoT TestBed publication.** 2022. <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7417349>
36. **Analog devices lt8210 datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-29-11. [Reference Source](#)
37. **Analog devices lt3045-1 datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-29-11. [Reference Source](#)
38. **Analog devices lt8361 datasheet.** [Reference Source](#)
39. **Analog devices lt3094 datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-29-11. [Reference Source](#)
40. **Analog devices lt3081 datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-29-11. [Reference Source](#)
41. **Analog devices lt6015 datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-29-11. [Reference Source](#)
42. **Analog devices ltc4359 datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-29-11. [Reference Source](#)
43. **Analog devices ada4522 datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-29-11. [Reference Source](#)
44. **Analog devices ltc6363 datasheet.** Accessed: 2022-29-11. [Reference Source](#)
45. **Analog devices ltc2335-18.** Accessed: 2022-27-07. [Reference Source](#)
46. **Analog devices ltc2500-32.** Accessed: 2022-27-07. [Reference Source](#)
47. **Raspberry pi 4 model b by raspberry pi foundation.** Accessed: 2022-25-07. [Reference Source](#)
48. **Odroid c4 by hardkernel.** Accessed: 2022-25-07. [Reference Source](#)
49. **Rockpi 4 by radxa.** Accessed: 2022-25-07. [Reference Source](#)
50. **Jetson nano developer kit by nvidia.** Accessed: 2022-25-07. [Reference Source](#)
51. **Altium designer.** Accessed: 2022-11-04. [Reference Source](#)

- 52. **Kicad pcb designer**. Accessed: 2022-07-12.
[Reference Source](#)
- 53. **Altium designer**. Accessed: 2022-11-04.
[Reference Source](#)

- 54. **Blender org**. Accessed: 2022-12-09.
[Reference Source](#)
- 55. **Freecad**. Accessed: 2022-12-09.
[Reference Source](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

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Reviewer Report 24 July 2023

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Marco Eugeni

Universita degli Studi di Roma La Sapienza, Rome, Lazio, Italy

IoT devices which are deployed in real-environment and where there is no access to the power grid need to have their power consumption measured for evaluation and design purposes. A theoretical estimation of the current consumption in real environments is a very complex process and for this reason the authors propose the use of a real-time testbed system which can help to provide an estimate of the current usage based on the real environmental conditions.

The authors have described TestBed V2, which is an improved version of Testbed V1. The reviewers acknowledge that a lot of efforts was put in place for the design of the system, however the paper seems incomplete as it lacks a clear mention of performance results (graphs/tables) that can be compared to state-of-the-art systems.

Major revisions should be applied to the paper.

Major comments:

- The literature review needs to be more extended to include more recent papers. Some references go back to 2009 (SANDBed [21][22]). For example the following paper could be assessed by the authors: Y. H. Tehrani and S. M. Atarodi, "Design & Implementation of High Dynamic Range Current Measurement System for IoT Applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, pp. 1-9, 2022, Art no. 2003009, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2022.3169538¹.
- In the paper it should clearly be indicated what is the novelty / the differences between the presented system and the state-of-the-art solutions.
- The paper should also include a table / graph comparing the performances of the proposed system with the ones available in the literature.
- A system architecture diagram of the testbed V2 should be included to add more clarity on the system functions and input/outputs, etc.

- The discussion section should provide an analysis of the results.
- A conclusion section is missing.

Minor comments:

- In the introduction, the authors provide a definition of IoT in the following sentence: “for modern Internet of Things (IoT) systems, which are typically represented as a combination of a wireless sensor network (WSN) and a data processing block1,2”. Can you indicate where in these papers [1] and [2] such definition has been given?
- In the text, some references to sections miss the section title/number.
- Figure 2 appears in reference [13]. The figure caption should contain the reference where the figure was taken from.
- In Equation (1) F_s should be the sampling frequency.
- In some parts of the paper “Shunt ammeter” is written shut ammeter. Please correct. The English should be improved in some sections of the manuscript.
- Please check again in paper [19] the value of the Current measurement maximum range (It should be 45 mA).
- In Figure 9, the ranges and the units are missing in the axes.

References

1. Tehrani Y, Atarodi S: Design & Implementation of High Dynamic Range Current Measurement System for IoT Applications. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*. 2022; **71**: 1-9
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Smart Manufacturing for space systems, IoT, space structures

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 05 Dec 2023

Rihards Balass

Dear reviewer, thank you for the review! We have improved the manuscript as you suggested and considered your suggested improvements. We have also prepared the answers to the questions you have raised:

1. The literature review needs to be more extended to include more recent papers. For example the following paper could be assessed by the authors: Y. H. Tehrani and S. M. Atarodi, "Design & Implementation of High Dynamic Range Current Measurement System for IoT Applications"
 1. Thank you for suggesting the paper to look at, we have included it into this article, we have also been looking at more recent papers regarding the current consumption measurements in IoT systems. While there are multiple papers discussing the energy consumption of IoT devices, they are mostly about the current consumption for devices that are connected to the power grid.
2. In the paper it should clearly be indicated what is the novelty / the differences between the presented system and the state-of-the-art solutions.
 1. We have created a table that shows the differences between the identified testbed facilities with current measurement capabilities and the TestBed v1 facility.
3. The paper should also include a table / graph comparing the performances of the proposed system with the ones available in the literature.
 1. We have created a table that shows the differences between both versions of EDI TestBed. Together with the table described in previous comment, it can be seen how this research and the developed device impacts the IoT current consumption field.
4. A system architecture diagram of the testbed V2 should be included to add more clarity on the system functions and input/outputs, etc.
 1. We have added a block diagram of the proposed TestBed v2.
5. The discussion section should provide an analysis of the results.
 1. We have improved the discussion section with an analysis of the results.
6. A conclusion section is missing.
 1. We have added a conclusion section to the paper.
7. In the introduction, the authors provide a definition of IoT in the following sentence: "for modern Internet of Things (IoT) systems, which are typically represented as a combination of a wireless sensor network (WSN) and a data processing block1,2". Can

you indicate where in these papers [1] and [2] such definition has been given?

1. There has been a mistake in the manuscript editing process which has been fixed. We have also rewritten the paragraph so it would be understood better.
8. In the text, some references to sections miss the section title/number.
 1. Since the Europe Open Research template does not contain numbering for the sections, this was missed. We have fixed the issue.
9. Figure 2 appears in reference [13]. The figure caption should contain the reference where the figure was taken from.
 1. The figure was made by one of the authors of this paper. Nonetheless we have added a reference to the original paper as well.
10. In Equation (1) F_s should be the sampling frequency.
 1. Fixed.
11. In some parts of the paper "Shunt ammeter" is written shut ammeter. Please correct. The English should be improved in some sections of the manuscript.
 1. We have gone through the paper and fixed spelling errors.
12. Please check again in paper [19] the value of the Current measurement maximum range (It should be 45 mA).
 1. Fixed.
13. In Figure 9, the ranges and the units are missing in the axes.
 1. We have added the missing axes, although they are not as clearly visible as we would like. To remedy that we added the explanation in the caption of the figure.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 27 June 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.16378.r32554>

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Carmen Delgado Pinillos

i2cat Foundation, Barcelona, Spain

This paper presents the design of a power meter for IoT devices. Since there are too many IoT devices, which are normally powered by batteries and these batteries have dangerous chemicals, being aware of the battery usage and how to make the best use of it is crucial. Authors try to solve this by proposing this device, capable of measure the current consumption.

This is the second version of their testbed, and the reviewer has the feeling that the information is a bit mixed. The paper talks about V1 in order to explain the weaknesses that the V2 tries to solve,

but this should be clearer explained. Authors could include a table with the differences of the two versions.

The state of the art could be better formulated by making sure the differences between previous works are detailed. For example, when explaining 3, 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17.

Apart from this, the details of the design and implementation are clearly explained and the device might be very useful in many applications.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: IoT, batteryless devices, resource allocation, energy modelling

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Author Response 05 Dec 2023

Rihards Balass

Dear reviewer, thank you for the review! We have improved the manuscript as you suggested and considered your suggested improvements. We have also prepared the answers to the questions you have raised:

1. The paper talks about V1 in order to explain the weaknesses that the V2 tries to solve, but this should be clearer explained. Authors could include a table with the differences of the two versions.
 1. We have created a table that shows the difference between both versions of TestBed.
2. The state of the art could be better formulated by making sure the differences

between previous works are detailed. For example, when explaining 3, 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17.

1. We have rewritten the text with emphasis on the differences and additions from each of the papers mentioned.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.